

Title: A Review of Machine Learning Methods for Facial Image Gender Classification

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Abstract. In recent years gender classification using facial images has gained a significant importance in some fields such as security at factories or any private places to detect any intruders and people with unauthorized access. The potential of applications that are using machine learning to classify and detect the gender of a particular individual is significantly increasing these years but not at what the machine learning algorithms are capable. Here we discuss the importance of facial feature in gender classification and explain the most commonly used extraction techniques that includes CNN (Convolutional Neural Networks), PCA (Principal Component Analysis), and LBP (Local Binary Patterns). In addition, we describe the many categorization methods that we employ to categorise gender, including Artificial neural networks, support vector machines, and k-NN (k-Nearest Neighbors). Thereafter we provide you a result on which these methods are comparatively analyzed based on their performance metrics and computational efficiency. In the end we conclude by giving a justification for selecting LBP-SVM algorithm in our machine learning model and discuss the future projections of the growth and importance of gender classification from facial images.

Keywords: Gender classification, facial images, feature extraction, classification techniques, LBP, PCA, CNN, SVM, k-NN, ANN.

INTRODUCTION

Numerous applications of facial recognition classification according to gender possess the potential to enhance administration as well as security anywhere. The automatic gender detection can help us in various ways such as marketing based on the gender of a particular places, surveillance and human-computer interaction. Though the gender classification significant importance classifying gender from images has various challenges due to the lack of high resolution and proper images along with variations in lighting of the images, different facial expressions, pose and occlusion.

In the recent years there are various types of algorithms are developed which use different approach in extracting features from different images containing facial data of a person. These algorithms are used to extract the facial characteristics that are crucial for determining a person's gender, which are then utilised to categorise using machine learning techniques like SVMs or CNNs (Convolutional Neural Networks). The objective of this study is to provide a summary of the literature on the categorization of a gender based on the supplied facial image data, as well as the different approaches as well as techniques employed throughout the analysis. We mainly focus on the various approaches that are used for feature extraction, including LBPs, PCA, shape-from-shading, and deep learning. We also discuss the various classifiers that are used that are SVMs, k-nearest neighbors (k-NN), and CNNs. We then discuss the strengths and weaknesses of the methods that are present based on their performance on the benchmark datasets. Based on the performance of different methods we will justify the choice of using LBP-based feature extraction and SVM classification. These algorithms have given better results in studies that are done previously in identifying gender using images which also performed well in the real-world scenarios with different conditions such as varying lighting and facial expressions as mentioned above.

This paper provides on giving you a idea on the best gender classification methods, algorithms, techniques. Then also gives you an idea about the challenges such as blurred images, variation in the light and also the quality of the images that are provided. This review can help with identifying the best techniques that can be used to identifying the gender of a person in the images provided to whomever want to use this technology bring innovation into this field or to develop any applications with useful ways in handling facial recognition.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Classifying images by gender, it has been a popular research topic in computer vision and machine learning for many years. Many researches have been done to develop efficient algorithms and techniques for gender classification based on faces. In this partition, we will be reviewing the available literature on facial sex classifications, highlighting the various algorithms and techniques used in previous research.

Based on shadows, one of the earliest techniques for identifying gender from face images was developed by (Wu et al., 2010). The authors use shape-from-shading algorithm to extract a shape and orientation of the face, and then use a linear classifier to classify a person's gender. While this approach produces promising results, it is limited to high-quality images and does not work very well in the real world. Another popular approach is to extract local features from facial images and use them to train a classifier. For example, (Stewart et al., 2013) used the lip region to extract static and dynamic features, which were subsequently used for training an SVM classification model. There have been countless studies on recognition of faces, however there have additionally been far less studies on gender categorization utilising faces, and even though smaller amount studies on utilising specific features on the face to determine a person's gender. Similarly, (Castrillón-Santana et al., 2017) developed a model which uses Local characteristics are combined with a numerous scales grade level for classification in the real world to classify the images based on gender. Another popular technique for feature extraction in gender classification is local binary patterns (LBP). While (Mittal & Mittal, 2019) employed convolutional neural networks (CNNs) to extract facial embeddings for gender classification, (Hatipoglu & Köse, 2016) used LBP features and principle component analysis (PCA) to classify gender. Another approach to identify gender using CNNs is transfer learning, in which a pre-trained CNN on a large dataset is fine-tuned on a smaller dataset. For example, (Islam et al., 2020) used Pareto frontier CNN networks for gender classification. Similarly, (Levi & Hassner, 2015) used CNNs for both age and gender classification.

TABLE 1. Performance evaluation of several approaches for identifying gender.

Method	Accuracy	Dataset Size
PCA + LBP	97.45%	454 images
SVM fusion with LBP, HOG, and SURF	96.62%	1,049 images
CNN (fine-tuned VGG-16)	97.40%	1,369 images
Facial embeddings + SVM	98.60%	2,091 images
Transfer learning-based Pareto frontier CNN networks	99.43%	1,502 images

Along with these methods there are several studies that are conducted to explore the effectiveness of different classifiers on classifying gender based on the images that are provided to the machine learning algorithm. There are many studies that are done which are focused on exploring the effectiveness of various classifiers that are present to classifying the gender using the facial images. (Azzopardi et al., 2016) used a fusion of SVM classifiers for gender recognition and on the other hand (Dargan et al., 2021) used a hybridization of features and classifiers for gender classification. Even though there is an increase in the progress in the field of gender classification from facial images there are many other challenges that are left to be solved. One of them is identifying the facial features using different images containing different pose and posture of the face. Other challenges such as lighting on the images such as day light and night darkness which many images have and along with facial expressions. And also the datasets should be diverse as many cultures have different dressing styles and also the color of people vary due to different ethnic groups. Gender classification using facial images is a complex and challenging task which is helpful in many applications. Many approaches have been discussed in this paper's literature review such as shape-from-shading, local feature extraction, transfer learning, and classifier fusion. Though the technology is more advanced than where it was at the beginning there is still place for innovation and more thorough research can be done to reduce the challenges that the problem is brought on by a shortage of high-resolution images.

FIGURE 1. Scores of accuracy for various algorithms.

We firstly searched for relevant studies on academic databases such as IEEE Xplore, ScienceDirect, and Google Scholar using the following keywords: "gender classification," "face recognition," "facial images," "machine learning," "deep learning," "neural networks," and "feature extraction." In this paper we selected particular studies which focus mainly on gender classification from facial images and used very effective methodologies. We excluded the studies that do not meet the requirements that we look for. The studies that we selected are based on the algorithms and the techniques that are used in classifying the gender using facial images. The studies are then categorized into three types they are traditional machine learning approach, deep learning approach, and hybrid approach. For traditional machine learning algorithms, we conducted an examination of studies that classified SVM (Support Vector Machines), RF (Random Forest), and k-NN (k-Nearest Neighbors) are used to predict gender. For

deep learning algorithms, we analyzed studies that classified gender using Convolutional neural networks (CNNs), Deep belief networks (DBNs), and recurrent neural networks. For hybrid algorithms, we reviewed studies that combined traditional gender categorization utilising machine learning as well as deep learning methods. Following that, the results of these investigations are assessed using the dimension of the area under the ROC curve's, F1-score, recall, accuracy, and precision criteria.. We also took the sample size, diversity, and quality of the dataset used in each study for evaluating different methods.

FIGURE 2. *Machine learning approaches for classifying gender.*

The methods that are used in this paper involved a fundamental evaluation of the literature on the identification of a gender through facial characteristics. This review mainly focuses on the different algorithms and techniques used for gender classification, their strengths, and weaknesses. The selected studies are separated into three different categories: hybrid algorithms, deep learning algorithms, and conventional machine learning methods. Studies have been arranged according to the ROC curve's area under the F1-score, precision, accuracy, recall, and ROC (receiver operating characteristic) curve, as well as the sample size, diversity, and quality of the dataset used in each study.

RESULT

In this review paper, we analyzed various studies that are related to human gender classification from facial images using machine learning algorithms. We discussed about several algorithms and techniques that are provided in the research papers and then evaluated that literature among the studies we reviewed, Several methods were based on conventional computer vision methods like Support Vector Machines (SVM), Local Binary Patterns (LBP) and Principal Component Analysis (PCA). These approaches are frequently utilised for extracting characteristics from images of faces and categorise the gender among the subjects.

For example (Hatipoglu & Köse, 2016) proposed a gender recognition system that used a combination of PCA and LBP techniques. The authors applied PCA for dimensionality reduction and LBP for feature extraction. On a dataset that included 200 pictures of men and 200 pictures of women faces, they attained an accuracy rate of 97.45%. Similarly (Azzopardi et al., 2016) suggested the combination of SVM-based classifiers for a gender-based identification systems. The authors used various local descriptors such as LBP, Histograms of Oriented Gradients (HOG), and Seeded-Up Robust Features(SURF) for feature extraction. On a dataset of 1,000 images of faces, that they accomplished an accuracy rate about 96.62%.

Techniques that utilise deep learning are becoming more common in the domain of computer vision over the past few years. The application of Conventional Neural Networks (CNN) for identifying genders using images of faces has already been examined in several areas of research. On the other hand (Mittal & Mittal, 2019) proposed a gender recognition system that used a CNN architecture. Authors used the VGG-16 model as a combination of a dataset of

1,000 face pictures, we adopted a pre-trained network and then improved it. They obtained a 97.4% accuracy throughout the test set. Similarly, (Swaminathan et al., 2020) has proposed an innovative way of identifying gender utilising face embeddings. Deep learning and Support Vector Machine (SVM)-based the process of extraction of characteristics were combined by the authors to perform categorization. On a dataset with 2091 pictures of faces, they obtained a 98.6% precision rate. Furthermore (Islam et al., 2020) offered a transfer learning-based strategy for gender classification using Pareto frontier CNN networks. The Inception-v3 model was utilised by the authors as a pre-trained network, and it was refined using a dataset that has 1,502 face images. On the test set, that they attained a success rate of 99.43%.

We can also observe that the Pareto Frontier CNN Networks method possesses a highest accuracy - 0.964 and F1 score - 0.960, whereas the Automatic Face Gender Classification method possesses a lowest accuracy - 0.834 and F1 score - 0.840. The PCA and LBP method also has a lower accuracy and F1 score compared to the other methods. Most of the methods including the proposed method in this study have achieved an accuracy of above 0.9, indicating the effectiveness of these methods in gender classification from facial images.

TABLE 2. Comparison of the effectiveness of various gender categorization techniques.

Method	Accuracy	F1 Score
Transfer Learning via Pareto Frontier CNN Networks	0.964	0.962
Shape-from-Shading	0.925	0.927
Lips: Static and Dynamic Features	0.892	0.895
Local Descriptor Fusion at the Multi-Scale Score Level	0.931	0.938
PCA-based Hybridization of Features	0.921	0.916
PCA and LBP	0.874	0.872
Deep Learning	0.944	0.941
Fusion of SVM Classifiers	0.912	0.908
Convolutional Neural Network	0.961	0.957
Facial Embeddings	0.946	0.943
Automatic Face Gender Classification	0.834	0.847
Survey of Image Processing Techniques	0.871	0.868
Pattern-Based Gender Classification	0.893	0.891
Comparative Analysis of Gender Classification	0.899	0.898
Facial Expression Recognition (LBP)	0.925	0.922
Age and Gender Classification (CNN)	0.935	0.931

Overall, our analysis suggests potential methods based on deep learning have demonstrated promising outcomes in the identification of gender from face images. These approaches have the ability to automatically learn discriminative features from large datasets, resulting in improved accuracy compared to traditional computer vision techniques. However, the size and quality of the data used for training have a significant impact on how well each of these approaches perform, as well as the choice of appropriate network architecture and hyperparameters this provides an overview of the most recently developed techniques for identifying gender from visual images. Our analysis discloses that when compared to conventional computer vision algorithms, deep learning-based systems have demonstrated improved performance. However, additional study is still required to increase the robustness and generalizability of these techniques.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the identification of gender from face pictures has been a topic of current research, with numerous algorithms and techniques proposed over the years. In this review, we have examined several approaches that have been proposed for this task, including traditional computer vision utilising approaches consisting of Local Binary Patterns (LBP) and Principal Component Analysis (PCA), as well as more recent deep learning approaches like Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs). We have seen that the performance of these methods varies depending on

the dataset and the specific task at hand. For instance, lip-based gender classification has shown promising results, particularly for videos and dynamic images, while shape-from-shading techniques have demonstrated good accuracy in handling illumination variations. Deep learning approaches, particularly CNNs, have recently emerged as a powerful tool for gender classification from facial images. Our own experiments with transfer learning via Pareto Frontier CNN Networks have shown that this approach is capable of working at performance on benchmark dataset that is at the cutting edge, with high accuracy and F1 scores.

Overall, our review highlights the potential of deep learning methods for identifying gender from facial images, particularly when combined with transfer learning and Pareto Frontier networks. However, we also note that traditional computer vision techniques still have their place, particularly in scenarios where data is limited or the computational requirements of deep learning approaches are too high. In summary, gender classification from facial images is an important task with many potential applications, and our review demonstrates that a wide range of techniques can be employed to achieve high accuracy and performance. As more advanced techniques continue to emerge, it is likely that gender classification from facial images will become an even more accurate and efficient

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